

A Network Analysis Approach to Identifying Rat-Running Hotspots in Bogotá, Colombia.

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Summary

Congestion in urban areas can also lead to an increase of vehicle flows across residential areas impacting road safety and infrastructure. Authorities have very limited information to identify and address the presence of rat-runs. We propose a network-analysis method based on betweenness centrality and employing open data to identify places in Bogota's road network that are likely to become rat-runs. It was possible to identify the 5% of the residential roads that, under congested conditions, provide faster routes for drivers. These findings can inform the strategic deployment of traffic calming measures to mitigate the impact of rat-runs.

KEYWORDS: road network analysis, open data, residential roads, through-traffic, rat-running

1 Introduction

The growth of car ownership has led to increasing congestion in urban areas worldwide (OECD, 2017). An annual report released by TomTom (2024) showed that in 2023, almost 60% of a sample of 387 cities experienced a reduction in the average speed of private cars. Increased congestion causes a spillover effect, pushing motor vehicles away from congested roads, as drivers seek alternative routes i.e. rat-runs to avoid delays. For example, navigation apps providing faster routes on demand have been reported to increase traffic on local roads across residential areas in the UK in recent years (Flint, 2015; Reid, 2020). Rat-running itself is not considered as a traffic offence; however, this unintended use of local roads, which are not designed to handle significant flows of vehicles moving at high speed, can negatively impact road safety and lead to rapid deterioration of the infrastructure (Albalate & Fageda, 2021).

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Delivering a comprehensive road network design is the most effective strategy for preventing drivers from using local roads as rat-runs and ensuring the safety of all road users (Global Designing Cities Initiative & National Association of City Transportation Officials, 2016). Since the current structure of urban road networks has evolved organically, influenced by various planning policies (Barthelemy, 2018), retrofitting the entire network would require significant resources. In a context of limited traffic flow data across the network, some local authorities have relied on citizen reports to identify areas that require interventions e.g. Bogotá CO (Medina, 2019), Concord USA (Town of Concord, 2019), and Leeds UK (Leeds City Council et al., 2024).

This research aims to explore how a network-analysis-based method can help identify plausible hotspots of rat-running in Bogotá. The study’s policy relevance is two-fold: informing the delivery of traffic calming interventions and supporting the allocation of traffic management officials.

2 Methodology

To identify alternative routes for drivers through local roads (i.e. rat-runs), the proposed method employs the road network graph representation to estimate the relative importance of residential streets by calculating the Betweenness Centrality (BC) (Freeman, 1977; Girvan & Newman, 2002) under typical traffic conditions.

In a distance-weighted network, the BC for each street is the total number of shortest paths passing through that link. For this study, we use the travel-time-weighted network to capture the effects of congestion, so BC corresponds to the number of quickest paths passing through the link. As a consequence, the BC of roads varies along the day as traffic flows affect the travel speed of vehicles (Daniel et al., 2020), i.e. vehicles tend to reduce their speed where there is more traffic. Although drivers may consider several elements when choosing an optimal route (Ortúzar & Willumsen, 2011); for this research, travel time is assumed to be the only determinant for short-term route choice leading to rat-running i.e. routes with the shortest travel time are preferred.

As illustrated in Figure 1, Bogotá’s road network was extracted from OpenStreetMap (OpenStreetMap contributors, 2024) using `osmextract` (Gilardi & Lovelace, 2024), and subsequently processed with `dodgr` (Padgham, 2019) to obtain the graph representation. Data on observed travel speed along major roads was obtained from Bogotá’s open data portal (Secretaria Distrital de Movilidad, 2022), and subsequently processed to obtain the 2019 typical hourly speed profile for weekdays and weekends. Mid and low-hierarchy roads with no speed data were assigned travel times based on posted speed limits (60 km/h for major roads, 30 km/h for minor roads). Based on the speed profile, the hour with the highest median speed (03:00) was selected as a baseline, as it is assumed that drivers utilise the network as intended during the least congested hour i.e. major corridors are preferred for their lower travel times, while local and residential roads serve only as access links.

Once travel times were adjusted for all roads from 00:00 to 23:00, BC was calculated for each hour and compared to the baseline BC. Road links with differences in the first decile are identified for each hour. Finally, the number of times roads are classed in the first decile is summed to produce a rat-run potential index, indicating how often the roads provide faster routes.

Figure 1: Schematic of proposed method

3 Results

Bogotá's road network extends over 6,590 kilometres (see Figure 2). Major roads, including trunk, primary, and secondary links, represent approximately one-fifth of the network length, yet they accommodate a significant portion of the city's traffic. On the other hand, residential roads make up nearly two-thirds of the total network length.

Observed speed data covers only a portion of the total length of major roads: 40% of primary roads, 20% of trunk roads, and 10% of secondary roads. As shown in Figure 3, travel speeds on major roads in Bogotá are highest during the first four hours of the day, often exceeding the speed limit of 60 km/h. On a typical weekday, speeds start decreasing significantly as traffic increases after 5:00 AM. Speed levels remain relatively constant throughout the day until the evening peak at 6:00 PM when the lowest speeds are observed. After this peak, speeds gradually increase as traffic eases.

The evening peak reduction in travel speed along major corridors results in changes in the BC distribution across all road types. As depicted in Figure 4, significant differences in BC are found within or in the vicinity of the major roads with observed speed data. Over 80% of trunk and primary roads exhibit a reduction in BC relative to the baseline. Moreover, half of these roads demonstrate a significant BC reduction (less than -5). For roads in the lower hierarchy, around 60% of secondary and residential roads, and 50% of tertiary roads show a reduction in BC. Also, while the proportion of links with high reductions is smaller in these road classes, a significant proportion of low hierarchy classes show big increases (greater than 5).

Figure 2: Road network in Bogota

(a) Profile by road segment

(b) Normalised speed across all road segments. Median and IQR.

Figure 3: Daily speed profile in major roads during weekdays and weekends.

(a) Spatial distribution

(b) Empirical cumulative distribution by road class

Figure 4: Differences in betweenness centrality for the weekday's PM peak compared to baseline

The potential for residential roads to be used as rat-tuns, based on shorter travel times during weekdays, is shown in Figure 5. According to the results, 80% of the residential roads have a low potential (≤ 2), while 5% are very likely to be used as rat-runs as they provide faster routes for drivers at least 20 hours of the day. A high-level exploration reveals that plausible rat-runs run parallel to a major road or connect two high-hierarchy roads through residential areas.

Figure 5: Rat-run potential on a weekday

4 Conclusions

This paper has presented the use of a network-analysis-based method to predict the presence of rat-runs in Bogotá's road network using open data. By using this approach, it was possible to identify the 5% of the residential roads that can likely serve as rat-runs under congested conditions.

This method offers an accessible way to explore how drivers use the road network. As a simplified approach, it is worth noting that several elements have not been considered in this study which could affect travel times, for example, road geometry, the presence of traffic calming interventions

or junction characteristics.

Future research will focus on exploring alternative datasets to mitigate the limited availability of traffic flow data for low-volume roads, thereby enabling the validation of rat-runs identified in this study. Potential datasets include reports of traffic offences from Bogotá's transport police force and crowd-sourced citizen reports.

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Biographies

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